

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazoles. Part IX : Acid Dissociation Constants of Ni(II) Complexes of 1-Benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2'-benzimidazolyl)ethane

N. N. GHOSH* and M. M. NANDI

Inorganic Chemistry Laboratory, University College of Science,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700009

Manuscript received 8 February 1978, revised 20 May 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

The acid dissociation of the complex $Ni(RH)_2$ in water-dioxan (1:1) at $\mu=0.5$ and $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ has been studied potentiometrically, where $RH_2 = 1$ -benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2'-benzimidazolyl)ethane. pK_2 and pK_1 have been determined by linear plots and are found to be 11.73 and 12.09 respectively. $Ni(RH)_2$ is soluble in excess alkali yielding a purple coloured solution evidently due to presence of $Ni(R)_2^{2-}$ anion in solution.

IN continuation of the work on metal complexing properties of biologically important sulphonamido-benzimidazoles¹⁻⁶, 1-benzenesulphonamido-1,2-bis(2'-benzimidazolyl) ethane (RH_2)⁷ has been taken under study. In our previous communication⁴ we have described the formation of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes with RH_2 following Irving and Rossotti titration technique⁸ in 1:1 water-dioxan. For Ni(II), titration was not possible after the completion of 1:1 complex formation due to precipitation of $Ni(RH)_2$ ⁵. However on addition of excess alkali, the precipitate would go into solution yielding a purple coloured solution which may be due to complex $Ni(R)_2^{2-}$ anion. The present paper describes the potentiometric determination of acid dissociation constants of the complex $Ni(RH)_2$ in 1:1 water-dioxan at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $\mu=0.5$ maintained by adding requisite quantity of $NaClO_4$, to study the formation of $Ni(R)_2^{2-}$ anion.

Experimental

The ligand RH_2 was prepared and purified following the method described in our earlier communication⁷. All other reagents were either AR quality or properly purified. The solutions were made in double distilled CO_2 -free water and purified dioxan⁹.

Measurements of pH values were made with Cambridge portable type pH meter using glass electrode of 1-13 pH range in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by means of an agar-2M $NaNO_3$ bridge. The pH-meter was calibrated with sodium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions in water with due temperature corrections.

Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml solutions in (1:1) water-dioxan of the following mixtures: (A) 0.008 M NaOH; (B) 0.01 M $HClO_4 + 0.02 M RH_2$, $(ClO_4)_2 + 0.002 M$ or 0.003 M $Ni(ClO_4)_2 + 0.08 M$ NaOH with 0.05 M $HClO_4$ solution in (1:1) water-dioxan. The $RH_2(ClO_4)_2$ was obtained *in situ* by mixing quantitatively RH_2 and $HClO_4$ in the molar ratios of 1:2. Ionic strength of the media was kept constant ($\mu=0.5$) throughout by adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$. Duplicate titrations were made in each case under identical conditions.

Results

The stepwise acid dissociation constants of the RH_2^{2+} under identical conditions, have already been reported and pK_2^* , pK_1^* and pK_1^* values have been found to be 2.77, 4.89 and 10.43 respectively⁷.

The acid dissociation for the complex $Ni(RH)_2$ may be represented as:

Now at any stage of the titration after attainment of equilibrium, the relations

$$M = M_2 + M' + M' \quad \dots (3)$$

$$R = 2M + R_2 + R_2 + R_1 + R_0 \quad \dots (4)$$

and as the solution is electroneutral hold good :

$$P + H^+ + 2R_2 + R_2 = 2M + F + F' + OH^- + R_0 + M' + 2M' \quad \dots (5)$$

where M, R, F, F' and P are initial concentrations of Ni(II), RH_2^{2+} , free acid added, free acid originally present and alkali respectively; and $M_2, M', M', R_2, R_2, R_1, R_0, H^+$ and OH^- are equilibrium concentrations of $Ni(RH)_2, Ni(RH)(R)^-, Ni(R)_2^{2-}, RH_2^{2+}, RH_2^+, RH_2, RH^-$, acid and alkali respectively.

In order to determine the concentration of OH^- ion a graphical method was employed. For this purpose, pH values at various stages of titration (A) were plotted against the negative logarithm of calculated OH^- concentrations. The alkali concentrations were obtained from the corresponding pH values.

The average number (\bar{n}_H) of the protons bound to the complex ion $Ni(R)_2^{2-}$ is given by

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{2M_2 + M'}{M} \quad \dots (6)$$

It can be deduced from equations (3-6)

$$\bar{n}_H = 4 - \frac{(P + H^+ - F - F' - OH^-)}{M + R_0} \left(1 - \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} - \frac{2[H^+]^3}{k_1^* k_2^* k_3^*} \right) / M \dots (7)$$

where $R_0 = (R - 2M) / \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^*} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{[H^+]^3}{k_1^* k_2^* k_3^*} \right)$

\bar{n}_H values are plotted against pH (Fig. 1) and the successive dissociation constants k_2 and k_1 have been evaluated by linear plot of the equation (8)

$$\frac{(2 - \bar{n}_H)}{\bar{n}_H} [H^+]^2 = \frac{(\bar{n}_H - 1)}{\bar{n}_H} [H^+] k_2 + k_1 k_2 \dots (8)$$

which may be deduced from (6).

Calculated curve have been shown along with the experimental points (Fig. 1). Standard deviation and limits of error have also been determined following usual procedure and results are stated in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Acid dissociation curve of $Ni(RH)_2$: 0.003M $Ni(II)$, O; 0.002M $Ni(II)$, ●; Calculated curve using $pK_2 = 11.73$ and $pK_1 = 12.09$.

TABLE 1. ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF COMPLEX $Ni(RH)_2$.

Species	pK_2	pK_1	Standard deviation (Range)
$Ni(RH)_2$	11.73 ± 0.03	12.09 ± 0.03	± 0.014 ($0 < \bar{n}_H < 1.5$)

Discussion

The three successive acid dissociations of the ligand RH_2^{2+} are due to deprotonation of two benzimidazolium ion and the third is due to deprotonation of $-SO_2-NH$ -hydrogen⁷. The study indicates the dissociation of two more hydrogen atoms from the complex $Ni(RH)_2$. The dissociation is probably from $-NH$ -group of benzimidazole ring the acidity of which enhances in presence of complex forming metal ions^{3,10,11}. The dissociation of hydrogen from benzimidazole ring in presence of metal ions was known long^{12,13} and several inner metallic complexes have been synthesised by various workers^{14,16}. Similar complexes are also isolated for imidazole and its derivatives¹⁷. Morris and Martin¹⁸ reported the deprotonation of the imidazole ring pyrrole nitrogen for the L-histidine, histamine and imidazole in presence of metal ions. pK_a values have also been determined. However X-ray crystallographic studies^{19,20} on structures of $Cu(4-MeIz)(NO_3)_2$ and $Zn(Iz)_4Cl_2$ (where 4-MeIz=4-methylimidazole and Iz=imidazole) confirm the coordination takes place

through tertiary nitrogen atom. But the dissociation of protons from pyrrole nitrogen atom in the pH range studied is only possible if there is any bonding with metal ions. This suggests the following equilibria in solution :

Specially in alkaline media the right hand side species predominates and deprotonation occurs. Therefore the structure of the purple $\text{Ni}(\text{R})_2^{2-}$ anion may be suggested as stated below, showing the coordination sites of the ligand RH_2 .

Standard deviation has been found to be ± 0.014 in the region $0 < \bar{n}_H < 1.5$. The deviation at $\bar{n}_H > 1.5$ may be due to overlapping of the complex formation steps. The deep pink colour in alkaline medium

is probably due to $\text{Ni}(\text{R})_2^-$ ion which slowly decolourised on addition of acid and a light green precipitate of $\text{Ni}(\text{RH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ results⁶.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to University Grants Commission for financial assistance.

References

1. N. N. GHOSH and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 35, 517.
2. N. N. GHOSH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 1909.
3. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 643.
4. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 778.
5. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 139.
6. M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 809.
7. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 331.
8. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1968, p. 177.
10. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 317.
11. N. N. GHOSH and M. N. MAJUMDER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 559.
12. S. SKRAUP, *Ann.*, 1919, 419, 1.
13. W. J. EILBECK, F. HOLMES and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, A, 757.
14. S. P. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 23, 710.
15. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1151.
16. M. GOODGAME and L. I. B. HAINES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, A, 174.
17. W. J. EILBECK, F. HOLMES, C. E. TAYLOR and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, A, 128.
18. P. J. MORRIS and R. B. MARTIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 1543.
19. B. K. LINDBERG, *Acta. Crysta.*, 1966, 21, 901.
20. H. MONTGOMARY and E. C. LINGAFALTER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 531.